

CAA2023

50 years of synergy

Amsterdam

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Abstract Book

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14. Robotics and Archaeology - on the state of the art and beyond

Daniel Carvalho, UNIARQ; FCT; LAQU

Location: E107

Robots are an integral part of contemporary society. From healthcare to manufacture, agriculture and industrial contexts, robots play fundamental roles, indispensable to maintaining and sustaining numerous systems. Archaeology, as well as various areas, utilizes robots in its endeavors: on the field, in laboratories, in presentations to the public. From automatic typologies to UAVs that reach the depths that humans can not fathom to venture, robots aid archaeologists in concluding their tasks, in an efficient and reliable way. Is it possible to go even further and elevate the role of robots within Archaeology? Are robots to be used as extensions and tools or can we conjoin them with Artificial Intelligence, and build an Artificial Archaeologist? In this session, we intend to discuss the present state of robotics in Archaeology and dwell on the possibilities that lie in the near future. Proposals, although not exclusive, would be very welcome on these lines of thought, both concerning eventual case studies and theoretical reflections: How do archaeologists use robots, in which circumstances and what are their benefits and drawbacks; Robots and the act of the excavation – should robots do fieldwork for us? How archaeologists can use robots for building knowledge and how would it affect the discipline; What should be the ethical concerns that surround the use of robots in Archaeology?

We encourage papers from students and ECR in different phases of their research, to provide a space for showing their ongoing work and progress.

SLOT 4

16:30 - 16:50 332. Envisioning the forthcoming era of robotics and automation in archaeology: a position paper

Arianna Traviglia (*Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)*)*; Ferdinando Cannella (*Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia*)

111. The contribution of robotic archaeology and automated controlled experimentation in use-wear analysis.

16:50 - 17:10

Joao MF Marreiros (*TraCER. MONREPOS-RGZM. ICAREHB, UAIG*)*; Ivan Calandra (*TraCER. MONREPOS-RGZM*); Geoff Carver (*TraCER. MONREPOS-RGZM*); Walter Gneisinger (*TraCER. MONREPOS-RGZM*); David Nora (*Hebrew University of Jerusalem*); Eduardo Paixao (*TraCER. MONREPOS-RGZM*); Hannah Rausch (*TraCER. MONREPOS-RGZM*); Jerome Robitaille (*TraCER. MONREPOS-RGZM*); Lisa Schunk (*University of Wroclaw*)

106. Marine robotic technologies and vision-based approaches within the underwater archaeological research

17:10 - 17:30

Eleni Diamanti (*NTNU*)*; Mauhing Yip (*NTNU*); Oyvind Odegard (*NO*); Annette Stahl (*Norwegian University of Science and Technology*)

89. Exploiting RFID Technology and Robotics in the Museum

17:30 - 17:50

Antonis Dimitriou (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Stella Papadopoulou (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*); Maria Dermenoudi (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*); Vasiliki Drakaki (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*); Andreana Malama (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Alexandros Filotheou (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Aristidis Raptopoulos Chatzistefanou (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Anastasios Tzitzis (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Spyros Megalou (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Stavroula Siachalou (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Aggelos Bletsas (*School of ECE & TSI, Technical Univ. of Crete*); Traianos Yioultsis (*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki*); Anna Maria Velentza (*University of Macedonia*); Sofia Pliasa (*University of Macedonia*); Nikolaos Fachantidis (*University of Macedonia*); Angela Moneda (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*)*; Evangelia Tsangaraki (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*); Dimitrios Karolidis (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*); Charalampos Tsoungaris (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*); Panagiota Balafa (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*); Angeliki Koukouvou (*Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki*)

384. Automated high-resolution ground-penetrating radar prospecting with an uncrewed ground vehicle at an archaeological site

17:50 - 18:10

Lieven Verdonck (*Archéologie et Philologie d'Orient et d'Occident, École normale supérieure, Paris*)*; Michel Dabas (*Archéologie et Philologie d'Orient et d'Occident, Ecole normale supérieure, Paris*)

The current work discusses such potentials through the prism of their usage in marine archaeological research. Mission planning, detection and identification of objects of interest, 2D/3D mapping and interpretation of UCH sites are based solely on visual perception and are investigated through various scales of autonomy (mission-time and offline). A comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art marine technologies and algorithmic solutions is reported, while the authors present samples of their ongoing research, in both simulation and real-world operations.

Since vision-based mapping is range-dependent, inevitably poses the dominant challenges of the underwater medium, like light attenuation, color absorption, turbidity, dynamics and refraction. Those challenges are escalating dramatically when no a priori knowledge is available and the area, where the robot navigates, is completely unknown. Recent literature presents promising steps towards intelligent path planning approaches for optimal collection and online assessment of visual data, collision avoidance and operational cost-effectiveness.

Sensor data must provide a situational awareness that is sufficient for both archaeological and operational decision making. Maneuvering and operation of a robotic platform must be sufficient precise and tactile to perform visual scanning in sites of delicate and fragile objects or in sites of high structural complexity.

In scenarios of existing basic a priori knowledge of a site's environment, mapping and documentation projects are first launched within simulation environments. Developing and working with synthetic datasets exceeds the cost-effectiveness of real world missions, as (nearly) all salient parameters of the site's geometry and prevailing conditions can be parameterized and controllable [3]. The vehicle's trajectories, the sensor's distances-viewpoints (sensors poses) or the desired spatial resolution are pre-estimated in a considerable level of accuracy.

The goals of a non-intrusive mission to document an identified wreck site can be defined in three tasks: a) simulate the environment mapping using a priori knowledge, to optimize sensor and parameter setup along with the motion planning, b) survey (initial data acquisition) of the entire site of interest and c) adaptive planning and perception to advance the initial data with respect to missing information and interest of detail with the underlying main aim to produce a dataset of high resolution and quality for interpretation and classification post mission. To be able to perform these three tasks in a roughly known environment, a robot must have certain capabilities. It must be able to autonomously navigate within the site while keeping track of its own position in relation to the spatial extent of the site (Visual SLAM or planning based on acoustic image/bathy), and it must be able to assess the quality of the optical images regarding turbidity, occlusions and light fields. In case the quality or coverage does not satisfy the mission goals, it must be able to adaptively re-plan tasks to remedy the situation.

Surveying extended geographic areas for the potential detection and classification of sites of UCH interest via autonomous robotic missions requires a lot of input data

from the maritime archaeologist during the initialization phase. Once the mission is launched, a great challenge that arises is to make the underwater vehicle's perception able to re-evaluate the overall assessment process and classification libraries based on new, growing data in mission-time. Decisions on the survey's boundaries as well as relevance and levels of importance of detected targets will be potentially made exclusively by robots, pushing notably autonomy limits. The up-to-today fiction idea of surveying, detecting and documenting an UCH site in the same dive is now highly considered.

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384. Automated high-resolution ground-penetrating radar prospection with an uncrewed ground vehicle at an archaeological site

Lieven Verdonck, *Archéologie et Philologie d'Orient et d'Occident, École normale supérieure, Paris*

Michel Dabas, *Archéologie et Philologie d'Orient et d'Occident, Ecole normale supérieure, Paris*

Although large progress has been made in geophysical data acquisition, the survey of large areas together with a high spatial resolution remains time-consuming even when using multiple sensors in parallel. In order to overcome this problem, one possibility is the use of uncrewed aerial vehicles. Tests with drone-borne electromagnetic induction instruments and magnetometers have been conducted.

Air-launched ground-penetrating radar (GPR) surveys were also tested, but result in decreasing reflection amplitudes (and therefore reduced penetration depth) and lower spatial resolution (Diamanti and Annan 2017, 1694). Therefore ground-based methods should also be explored.

A small, four-wheeled Clearpath Robotics Husky uncrewed ground vehicle (UGV), with a maximum speed of ~1 m/s and a payload of up to 75 kg, was tested to investigate its suitability for automated GPR prospection (Verdonck 2021, 220). It is equipped with wheel encoders, an inertial measurement unit (IMU), and a GNSS receiving corrections from permanent reference stations via mobile internet. Additional position measurements were obtained by tracking a prism placed on top of the Husky using a robotic total station. These allow the UGV to estimate its position, orientation and velocity, through data fusion by means of an extended Kalman filter, which is part of the Robot Operating System (ROS), an open source framework structured as a large number of small programs or 'nodes' (Quigley, Gerkey and Smart 2016).

In July 2021, the Husky was tested at the Roman town Falerii Novi (Italy), which was surveyed previously with a GPR array towed by an all-terrain vehicle. The UGV pulled two 500 MHz GPR antennae, covering an area of 1600 m². The objectives of the survey were to investigate (1) how accurately the robot can follow predefined survey lines; (2) if the robot can independently reach a series of predefined goals; (3) how well the UGV can avoid obstacles; (4) which sensors are essential for localization and navigation; and (5) possible interference between UGV and GPR.

The accuracy of the UGV when following predefined lines was tested at speeds of 0.3–0.9 m/s. Although there were cross-line errors of up to 0.2 m, for all speeds the errors were relatively consistent within and between traverses. As a consequence, the survey area was evenly covered, and sample density approximated theoretical requirements for 500 MHz GPR antennae. This resulted in time slices of the same quality as the ones collected with the human-driven GPR platform. Three manual interventions were necessary, when the UGV could not reach a waypoint, mainly because of wheel slippage in the shifting sand covering parts of the test site.

The UGV's ability to avoid obstacles was tested in two ways. A Velodyne VLP-16 LiDAR mounted in the front of the Husky allowed it to successfully avoid an obstacle of ~0.5 m x 0.3 m x 1 m. At the same time, long vegetation caused the LiDAR to identify a number of false positives, which made the Husky deviate from its path. This occurred more often when plants had thick stems, and less in the case of grass. Also, after having avoided the obstacle, the robot often did not return to the predefined transect line, but followed a parallel path to reach the next waypoint. This is because the ROS planner finds a path with minimal cost. This cost is only based on the distance from the target and from obstacles, not on the proximity from the original predefined

line. Alternatively, the position and dimensions of the obstacles can be measured with a GNSS before the start of the survey, and additional waypoints can be given to the UGV so that it can avoid the obstacles without using a LiDAR. This is more time consuming but led to good results at Falerii Novi.

Another question is which sensors are vital for the UGV to navigate. In order to obtain a precise position estimate, the wheel encoders (whether in combination with the IMU or not) were not sufficient, but RTK GNSS or the tracking total station were essential. To investigate which sensors are necessary to reliably calculate the robot's orientation, several sensor combinations were tried: GNSS–wheel encoders, GNSS–wheel encoders–IMU, and GNSS–wheel encoders–tracking total station. It was found that the UGV performed equally well using only GNSS–wheel encoders, and that the use of extra sensors such as IMU or tracking total station was not essential. At the moment, it is being investigated how accurately this single GNSS instrument can predict also the coordinates of the GPR antennae pulled behind the robot.

When measuring interference between the sensors mounted onto the UGV and the GPR antennae, the most important source of noise was the 900 MHz transmitter of the wireless emergency stop. It had to be kept at a distance of at least a few metres not to interfere with the GPR receiver.

After each transect, raw GPR data are automatically transferred from the notebook on the UGV to a base station computer for quality control in the field. A simple data processing flow was developed, including dewow, time zero correction, gain, background removal, conversion of GNSS coordinates to a projected coordinate system, calculation of individual antenna coordinates, and the creation of horizontal slices. Currently, the use of semi-automated interpretation algorithms based on convolutional neural networks is being investigated, both for rapid visualisation of the results as they are transferred by the UGV, and as an aid in the final delineation and interpretation.

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